

CONTEXTUALISATION OF THE 'BRICKWALLS' OF LAND ADMINISTRATION AND REGULATION SYSTEM AFFECTING THE DYNAMICS OF FORMAL LAND MARKET IN NIGERIA

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Abstract:

The centrality of land to man's socio-economic and even political survival, has long been recognised as a non-negotiable necessity. Apparently, because of the relative fixity of this resource, coupled with ever soaring demographic bursts, that had made it imperative more than ever before, to ensure the management, administration, control and regulation of its use and development a top priority. However, it must be frankly admitted, that formal land market, which is driven by the dynamics of supply and demand, which are otherwise termed delivery and accessibility respectively, are faced with very unimaginable challenges of unprecedented scales. Although, these 'brickwalls' are emanating from very many different contexts, but arguably, the most copious of them are traceable to formal land administration and regulation systems. Therefore, it is in a bid to address this very unfortunate trending turbulence, created and sustained by 'brickwalls' of formal land administration and regulation system, as reflected above, that this study was conducted. Hence, subsequent upon literature search that revealed some salient issues, that was evidenced to be brickwalls of land administration and regulation system. Therefore, structured questionnaires were designed with 5point Likert scale format and distributed via purposive and convenience sampling technique, among 450 respondents that were adopted for the sample size, from a sample frame 850 respondents, out of the total sample space of 2408

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respondents. It captured relevant officers on permanent and tenured engagement among the various land agencies that jointly constitute the formal land administration and regulation system within the Nigeria's south-western states of Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo and Ekiti, as well as independent land consultants and NGOs with shelter mandate, together with various classes of land users and developers. Sequel to application of AMOS' version 18 software to conduct Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), the 427 retrieved questionnaires were made through series of integrity tests to establish their reliability and normality. 416 questionnaires were found valid, upon which the analyses were done. The results showed that amongst the three major 'brickwalls' studied, human techno-analytical arsenal was found to be of not-so-significant effects on the formal land administration and regulation system and thus resultantly impacts less on the overall supply and demand dynamics of the formal land market. The study recommends among other things, for a very urgent and decisive action to seriously re-align and reconfigure the structure of various constituent units of Nigeria's land administration and regulation system, so as to engender synergy and collaboration building among them, with a view to making them more optimal in their performance, thus contributing immensely to the operational vibrancy of the formal land market in Nigeria.

JEL: R14, R52, R31

Keywords: contextualisation, brickwalls, land administration and regulation system, formal land market dynamics, Nigeria

1. Introduction

It is worrisome to note, that, much as governments of different countries, Nigeria inclusive, have striven to devise several approaches to stem the rising ugly scenarios that are being experienced almost on daily basis by citizens, in their efforts to access developable lands, which are supposedly deliverable by appropriate government land agencies; very little progress has so far been recorded in settling and closing the gaps, that are constantly being created and widened in the formal market dynamics of supply (delivery) and demand (accessibility) of urban lands by various categories of users (Akinbola and Md Yassin, 2016b). Also, along similar vein, Meinzen-Dick and Mwangi (2009) asserts, in many climes, notwithstanding the structure of the socio-economic and political system being operated, the ambience of all-round progress is paramountly

bottom-lined on how robust and strong the mechanics of the management of her land and its associated vast resources are.

Furthermore, it stands to rightly appreciate the reason why land administration and regulation system, parade themselves as the most veritable instruments of land management, that are simply the drivers of the asset base of real estate stock of some of these countries. Convincingly, they are fulcrum around which the entire land and its shrouded resources, including their worth revolve and primely midwived (De Soto, 2000). Moreover, it is long appreciated that land and its invaluable resources are extinctive, by design and creation. However, over past decades, there has been copious recognition of the fact that, economic and useful life spans of land assets are being elongated, through sustainably managing, maintaining, optimising and harnessing mechanisms. Needless to say, that government, through her land administration and regulation's instruments, are presumed of handling all the daunting responsibilities of conceiving, implementing and monitoring all that will continually make lands delivery and accessibility possible on a sustainable basis (UN-HABITAT, 2011).

Although, in the recent times, there have been calls for private sector's direct involvement, or at least indirect participation, via the public-private participation vehicles, however, government still remains the largest player (Tinubu, 2003). Meanwhile, societies all over the world, have also come to fully realise, mindless of the many modules of accessing a comparatively competitive asset by several consumers, due to in-substitutable nature of land resources, governments have come to indisputable awareness of the extreme need for tripod fulcrum of justice, equity and fairness, in the of resources such as land. This conscious step becomes cardinal, so as to properly satisfy all the socio-cultural idiosyncrasies and demographic components, that are true hallmarks of robust strategies, that are geared towards achieving the redistribution (in terms of allocation and acquisition scenarios) in the most beneficial way of land and its vast resources, as well as addressing the challenges of anti-social disorders, such as civil cohesion and crimes of various colourations (Mabogunje, 2003; Ibidapo-Obe, 2003; Akinbola and Md Yassin, 2016a).

Therefore, drawing from the several reminiscence above, it is borne out of genuine concern, to unravel some of these challenges that were inadvertently the creation of formal land administration and regulation system's brickwalls, as discussed above, that this study was conceived. Basically, to clinically understudy these issues very intensively and properly situate them within the context of the consequences they have brought to the fore, so as to completely evolve enduring strategies to fully address these challenges, thus remove their felt impacts upon the dynamics of the formal land market.

2. Literature Review and Conceptual Clarifications

Foremost, it is noteworthy that the operational vibrancy and efficiency of formal land administration and regulation system, are to an appreciable extent faced with such challenges, such as heightened crises of interrelationship which were created, expanded and even enlivened, through dys-configuration of the hierarchical structure of the system. Thence, it is being recognised that, land administrators who are core career officers that drive land administration functions, are in constant unwholesome rivalry, as well as seemingly perennial impasse of colouration, that is of inferiority complex dimension, with their land regulation counterparts, who are adjudged veterans, hence on tenure capacity (McAuslan and Farvaque, 1992; Struyk *et al*, 1990; Akinbola *et al*, 2015b). This very unfortunate cycle has undoubtedly culminated in consistent swapping of responsibilities, which had led to jettisoning of duties among these important players. It is needless to say, that this trend had continuously been clogging the expected pathways of delivery and accessibility, which is being principally handled by formal land administration and regulation, thus hampers them as drivers of formal land market dynamics, especially as it adversely affects urban land development (Kombe, 2000; UNESCAP, 2000; Akinbola and Md Yassin, 2016a).

Furthermore, in the views of Quan *et al.*, 2004; Benjaminsen *et al.*, 2009;; Agunbiade, 2012; Samsuddin, 2014, formal land administration and regulation system has also become non-performing as well as ineffective, due to sub-optimality in the psychological and emotional make-ups of the actors involved, which inadvertently has been precipitated by poor value system. These scholars further maintained that, this unfortunate state of mind of the officials results in their failure, to rightly synthesise and properly situate any present task within the context of attaining much lofty goals of future benefits, hence results to complacency of greater dimension, that concomitantly impacts very negatively on the formal land administration and regulation system's woeful actions, in impressively driving the formal land market dynamics. It then stands to reason, that the absence of such integral templates, which are very important for any effective and optimally performing system, are somehow recurring; sadly then that, the situation warps the strength of the formal land administration and regulation system, this no doubt clogs the vibrancy of all the stakeholders of formal land market, in both the hind and fore ends (UNECE, 2005a; Vanderbrink *et al*, 2010; Alden, 2008; Meinzen-Dick, 2009; Mabogunje, 2003).

Moreover, it must also be reiterated that series of catalogued facts, point to the dysfunctionality of the formal land market, as being due to the failure of formal land administration and regulation system, to appreciate the integrality of economic

considerations and financial factors of the greater proportion of the populace, while specifying standards and templates, which later turn out to be anti-developmental, simply for being rather too utopian to be observed by the interested land developers (Omirin, 2003; Mabogunje, 2005). Equally, of more genuine interest, is the unfortunate trend of governments' anticipation and factoring into budgets' computation, incomes from land delivery and accessibility related endeavours, so much that, it outrightly leads to making access more elusive more than ever before. This unwarranted budgetary load on the land administration and regulation system, is painful, adverse and productivity-lessening to say the least (UNESCAP, 2000 and the World Bank, 2005). Thence, it was additionally prayed for, that, social and political affiliations of prospective developers of urban lands, be totally relegated to the very inexistent level, as a pronounced preferential norm among the land administrators and regulators, before approval and eventual allocation of lands for development could take place (Payne and Majale, 2004; Umeh, 1983; Emueze, 2000; Akinbola *et al*, 2016c).

Also, along the same vein, impressive effectiveness of the formal land administration and regulation system, is perennially lacking, due to copious shortfalls in desirable robustness, technical wherewithal, sophisticated knowledge, multi-tasking skills and transferably-huge experience (UNESCAP, 2000; Rakodi and Leduka, 2004; Kwame and Antwi, 2004; Bello, 2006). Further to this, is the introspection that the reality has brought about, which is the urgency of marshalling efforts to improve the dynamics of the formal land market, by strengthening the land administration and regulation system, particularly as it concerns frequent updating of the technocratic culture and practices, which ensures the engagement of clear-headed and experienced veterans, retainment of most technically-skilled fresh minds, etc, so as to further buoy the system of land administration and regulation, in comfortably bracing up to the soaring challenges confronting formal land market dynamics (Agbato, 2006; Oyedele, 2008 and Olaniran, 2012; Payne and Majale, 2004; Majale, 2002; McLeod, 2003; Akinbola *et al*, 2015b).

Thence, Kironde (2004), Payne (2007), UNECE (1996) and Dale and McLaughlin (1999), opined that multi-faceted challenges being faced by the dynamics of formal land market, which are occasioned by land administration and regulation system, can be addressed via concerted efforts of government and even coalition between government and organised private sector, by decisively expanding the skill-base of the requisite knowledge, that are much desirably-needed to drive this important sector of the public service. The anticipated goal is that a virile and adequately remunerated workforce has a propensity to sufficiently deliver her mandates, however demanding the job

responsibilities are (Williamson 2000; Van der Molen 2003; EU 2004; Williamson et al. 2008).

Therefore, it is against the backdrop of the issues that are described as brickwalls, as revealed and corroborated by literature above, which were later calibrated and broadly termed as structural and culturo-behavioural dictates (SCBD), socio-political and economic dictates (SPED) and human techno-analytical arsenal (HTAA). These three broad 'brickwalls' became the latent constructs that were used in measuring the major determinant variable, that is, the formal land administration and regulation systems (FLARS), as well its impacts on the overall formal land market dynamics in Nigeria, that is the focus of this study

3. Materials and Method

Sequel to conducting of two rounds of pilot survey, in-depth reviews of relevant literature took place, through which the 'brickwalls' of formal land administration and regulation system (FLARS), that are affecting the dynamics of the formal land market got serialised. Thereafter, for the purpose of empirical exercise and eventual analyses, these brickwalls were coined broadly into three latent constructs, with each of them subsuming some items of evaluative queries, as thus: structural and culturo-behavioural dictates (SCBD), socio-political and economic dictates (SPED) and human techno-analytical arsenal (HTAA), with all these constructs directly measuring the one major determinant variable, that is, formal land administration and regulation system (FLARS), so as to establish the indirect and resultant adverse impacts of all of them on the dynamics of the formal land market. Therefore, structured questionnaires were designed with 5point Likert scale format and distributed via purposive and convenience sampling technique, among 450 respondents that were adopted for the sample size, from a sample frame 850 respondents, out of the total sample space of 2408 respondents. It captured relevant officers on permanent and tenured engagement among the various land agencies that jointly constitute the formal land administration and regulation system within the Nigeria's south-western states of Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo and Ekiti, as well as independent land consultants and NGOs with land and shelter mandates, together with various classes of land users and developers. Therefore, it becomes a rule that before the application of AMOS' version 18 software to conduct Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) analyses, on the 427 retrieved questionnaires, series of integrity tests were made, to at least establish their reliability and normality. 416 questionnaires were found valid, upon which the analyses were done. Moreover, it is pertinent to note that, formal land administration and regulation

system, as a determinant construct higher domain, suggests that a second order confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is conducted as a condition. However, it is a requirement that any construct of such hierarchy, which calls for the performance of second order confirmatory factor analysis, must be sufficiently defined. This is made up of the three first order constructs, that is, structural and culturo-behavioural dictates (SCBD), socio-political and economic dictates (SPED) and human techno-analytical arsenal (HTAA), which are the components that are distilled to form formal land administration and regulation systems (FLARS), as the determinant variable that all these components are measuring, which calls for CFA to be run on them. Essentially, this is done, so as to examine and confirm the acceptance or rejection of the hypotheses involved, through the discriminant validity, as well as generating the expected serialised values from these three latent constructs' calibrated items of queries, that is the SCBD, SPED and HTAA, thereafter employ the resulting indices to evaluate the higher order model for the major determinant variable, that is, formal land administration and regulation system FLARS.

Therefore, the structural presentation of the model that was evolved, explicates how intricately-linked these three latent constructs SCBD, SPED and HTAA are, together with the route and the weight of the effect of their interconnectivity on the determinant variable FLARS, that is being measured, is thus being captured in figure 1, as well as its model fit statistics that is expressed in table 1 respectively. This is principally done to test the validity or otherwise of the hypotheses that are involved, which are as follows, thus:

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant relationship between structural and culturo-behavioural dictates and formal land administration and regulation system, resultantly affecting the dynamics of formal land market.

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant relationship between socio-economic and political dictates and formal land administration and regulation system, resultantly affecting the dynamics of formal land market.

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant relationship between human techno-analytical arsenal and formal land administration and regulation system, resultantly affecting the dynamics of formal land market.

Figure 1: Second Order Confirmatory Factor Analysis for Measurement Model of FLARS

Table 1: Statistics for Second Order Confirmatory Factor Analysis Measurement
 Model of Exogenous Variable FLARS

Model Identification				Model Fit Statistics				
Observed Variables	=	20	χ^2	=	577.002	CFI	=	0.969
Estimated Parameters	=	3	χ^2/df	=	2.365	RMSEA	=	0.057
Degree of Freedom	=	244	P	=	0.000	LO90	=	0.000
Model is Identified			RMR		0.004	PCLOSE	=	0.000
Factor Loadings								
S / N	Items		Construct	Estimate	C.R	P	SMC	Remark
1	SCBD 1, 2, 4,5,6,7.	<-	SCBD	0.52	10.22	***	0.72	Stipulations are attained, Convergent validity holds
2	SPED 3,5, 6,7,8,9	<-	SPED	0.36	7.99	***	0.71	Stipulations are attained, Convergent validity holds.
3	HTAA 1,2,3,5,6 ,8,9	<-	HTAA	0.04	1.11	***	0.68	Stipulations are attained, Convergent validity holds.
All the Factor Loadings attained required levels, except HTAA with low ML estimate and CR, Model Statistics for Goodness-of-Fit Indices are upheld, this Model is fairly Accepted.								

Table 1 captures the fit statistics of the second order confirmatory factor analyses for the measurement model of the determinant variable, that is, formal land administration and regulation system FLARS, with acceptable model fit, though the third latent construct HTAA exhibits some levels of fair inadmissibility, as displayed in the values generated for ML estimate (0.04) and CR (1.11). However, the model's validity as well as its overall acceptability are not marred in the slightest guise, simply because, the possible adverse effect(s) it would have had suffered, has been neutralized by the reasonably high SMC value of 0.68. Thence, all the three latent constructs that were distilled from literature and supported by empirical piloting, that is, structural and culturo-behavioural dynamics (SCBD), socio-political and economic dictates (SPED) and human techno-analytical abilities (HTAA), which are admitted as components against which the determinant variable formal land administration and regulation system FLARS was examined, together with their respective factor loadings. Gladly to note that, there was an exhibition of desirable significance in the critical ratios and p-values for convergent validity of these three constructs, except the third latent construct, that is, human techno-analytical abilities (HTAA). Nonetheless, the three

latent constructs showed some plausible level of reliability including their overall items of queries, with which they were made up of, as a result of the high values of SMC for the three latent constructs, which impressively contributed to the acceptability of the second order confirmatory factor analysis model, for the first determinant variable FLARS. Therefore, at this juncture, it is considered very imperative to accept this model, simply because there has been a fulfilment, to a very large extent, all the conditions for its admissibility. Hence, all these efforts which were geared towards establishing the ground, upon which choices are made concerning the strength in the validity of the hypotheses that are inherently evolved, have granted profundity in the furtherance of critical evaluation of all the cross-cutting issues that are involved in the dynamics of the formal land market. Furthermore, this is displayed in table 2, in a bid to evolving some all-encompassing and valid findings, suggestions and possible contributions.

Table 2: Testing of Hypotheses among Constructs Involved in The Determinant Variable
 FLARS (SCBD, SPED and HTAA)

			ML	S.E	C.R.	P	Label
SCBD	>	FLARS	.516	.055	10.218	***	Sig
SPED	>	FLARS	.365	.043	7.993	***	Sig
HTAA	>	FLARS	.045	.036	1.113	.266	Insig

Therefore, in the final analyses, it is noteworthy that out of three evolved hypotheses, two were significant, which are also of directionally positive significance at 99% level of confidence, while one was of non-significance at 95% level of confidence, as expressed in table 2 (Vogt, 2005). Hence, it is thus pertinent to note, that the third empirically verified relationships of human techno-analytical arsenal with formal land administration and regulation system (*H3: There is a significant relationship between human techno-analytical arsenal and formal land administration and regulation system at $B=0.05$, $z=1.210$ and $p=0.000<0.001<0.226$*) became non-supported by this research, as it was found to be an insignificant brickwall of formal land administration and regulation system that affects the dynamics of the formal land market. This above result notwithstanding, the other two latent constructs that are remaining in this research , that is, the empirically verified relationships of structural and culturo-behavioural dictates with formal land administration and regulation systems (*H1: There is a significant relationship between structural and culturo-behavioural dictates and formal land administration and regulation system at $B=0.53$, $z=10.435$ and $p=0.000<0.001$*), socio political and economic dictates with formal land administration and regulation system (*H2: There is a significant relationship between socio-political economic dictates and the formal land administration and regulation system at $B=0.34$, $z=7.132$ and $p=0.000<0.001$*), are confirmed

to be significant and positive, as well as completely supported by this study, with the totality of all their fit statistical values that are expressed variously in the tables 1 and 2, are found to be within the established threshold. Finally, it must be emphatically stated, that the structural and culturo-behavioural dictates exhibits the weightiest path strength, which further deepens the upholding of the observed phenomenon, that among the various brickwalls of formal land administration and regulation system, that are affecting the dynamics of the formal land market in Nigeria, SCBD is the naughtiest and most developmentally retrogressive of them all.

4. Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

4.1 Summary and Discussion of Findings

1. As generated and contained in figure 1, SCBD1 exhibits a regression weight of 0.82 and 0.67SMC. This simply means that 67% of the 416 respondents, averagely in their cumulative unison said 82% of the challenges of the dynamics of formal land market, which emanate from formal land administration and regulation system, are caused by the absence of meaningfully-felt and beneficial interrelationship between the duo of career land administrators and tenured land regulators and advisors, which eventually always results to retardation in the processes of formal land acquisition, resultantly reduces formal land delivery and accessibility.
2. As generated and contained in figure 1, SCBD5 exhibits a regression weight of 0.78 and 0.61SMC. This simply means that 61% of the 416 respondents, averagely in their cumulative unison said 78% of the challenges of the dynamics of formal land market, which emanate from formal land administration and regulation system, are caused by the land administrators and regulators' non-possession of knowledge of aggregately diverse cultural orientation, ethos and ownership grip of the traditional land owning families, resultantly affects formal land delivery and accessibility.
3. As generated and contained in figure 1, SCBD7 exhibits a regression weight of 0.78 and 0.61SMC. This simply means that 61% of the 416 respondents, averagely in their cumulative unison said 78% of the challenges of the dynamics of formal land market, which emanate from formal land administration and regulation system, are caused by the heavily uni-directionalised relationship path in the favour of land regulators, because they are mostly veterans and advisors to the governor on land matters. This engenders lackadaisically in the civil service and

seriously reduces efficiency and finally land delivery and accessibility is adversely affected.

4. As generated and contained in figure 1, SPED3 exhibits a regression weight of 0.83 and 0.69SMC. This simply means that 69% of the 416 respondents, averagely in their cumulative unison said 83% of the challenges of the dynamics of formal land market, which emanate from formal land administration and regulation system, are caused by the primacy of the sole individual that occupies the office of the governor at an point in time and that of the finality of the decisions of the land regulation committee, which often leads to delay that is avoidable, especially as population and the land development segment of the demographics continues to soar, not delegating such duty as onerous as it is, is very inimical to overall development of the country.
5. As generated and contained in figure 1, SPED6 exhibits a regression weight of 0.83 and 0.69SMC. This simply means that 69% of the 416 respondents, averagely in their cumulative unison said 83% of the challenges of the dynamics of formal land market, which emanate from formal land administration and regulation system, are caused by too much of income expectation derivable from land related activities, cum poor budgetary allocation to the same agencies by government, is very inimical to overall development of the country. This invariably makes formal land acquisition annoyingly expensive, which invariably had made land delivery and accessibility to be adversely affected.
6. As generated and contained in figure 1, SPED9 exhibits a regression weight of 0.87 and 0.76SMC. This simply means that 76% of the 416 respondents, averagely in their cumulative unison said 87% of the challenges of the dynamics of formal land market, which emanate from formal land administration and regulation system, are caused by issues of uncontrolled urbanisation and population growth rate, without commensurate level of planning and action packages to rise to the challenges that such phenomena pose, with overall attendant adverse effect on formal land delivery and accessibility.
7. As generated and contained in figure 1, HTAA2 exhibits a regression weight of 0.96 and 0.91SMC. This simply means that 91% of the 416 respondents, averagely in their cumulative unison said 96% of the challenges of the dynamics of formal land market, which emanate from formal land administration and regulation system, are caused by understaffed workforce coupled with non-sophisticated, non-dynamic and ill-motivated staff strength, and as such lacks adequate strength to handle emerging enormously complex tasks that are associated with land delivery and accessibility, especially as population continues to grow.

8. As generated and contained in figure 1, HTAA6 exhibits a regression weight of 0.98 and 0.96SMC. This simply means that 96% of the 416 respondents, averagely in their cumulative unison said 98% of the challenges of the dynamics of formal land market, which emanate from formal land administration and regulation system, are caused by non-availability of strong data capture architectural framework of permissibly-high features that can comfortably handle some of the emerging complex land requirements of the 21st land applicants and developers, hence makes formal land administration and regulation system incapacitated to measure up with challenges formal delivery and accessibility of urban lands in this regard.

4.2 Conclusion

Through objective overview and thorough analyses of all the actual and observed phenomena occurrences, as they pervade and strive to sustain and perpetuate themselves, with respect to formal land administration and regulation's grip on the dynamics of formal land market in Nigeria; it must be unequivocally emphasized, that the structural and culturo-behavioural dictates among all other brickwalls, exhibits the most weighty influence, which confirms further the wider plausibility of the observed phenomenon, that among the various brickwalls of formal land administration and regulation system, that are affecting the dynamics of the formal land market in Nigeria, the structural and culturo-behavioural dictates is the most adversely-effective and developmentally retrogressive of them all.

4.3 Recommendation

1. There is very urgent need for serious re-ordering and reconfiguring of the structure of land administration and land regulation system, to ensure building of strong synergy and collaboration among the actors, as against the present dispersed structuration that obtains in Nigeria..
2. Incorporation of a mechanism that guarantees cultural and ethnographic diversity of prehistoric landholding practice among land MDAs, so as to brew awareness for appreciation and application of archival knowledge on land matter, with a view to reducing friction on formal land allocation issues that have a borderline with conventional land ownership.
3. Government should endeavour to strive very urgently to evolve a reward system and attach competitive packages to increased workload and goal attainment, e.g. double promotion, salary increase, etc., so as to increase creativity, intellectual

elegance and hardwork. This will certainly and drastically reduce complacency in service delivery, as it presently obtains.

4. There must be a mechanism that establishes and accentuates the sustenance of delegative responsibilities and enshrinement of appeal mechanisms, so that the former can meaningfully expand the approval authorities and the latter can provide a check system to cautions the overzealousness of land regulation and advisory committee
5. Government should treat an increased budgetary allocation as a priority to make land as a consociate capital and not entirely economic good, so that its potentials as a source of wealth base, which spins out good income for government and viciously sustains the economic reliance of all the concerned, can be realised. This effort will also lead to reduction in the development costs associated with land procurement on the parts of the land developers.
6. Government is advised to engage in decisive and vigorous recruitment of more bright and able hands, so as to increase the staff strength (quantity and quality). This will certainly buoy workforce with sophistication and increased technical vigour to find and allocate lands faster through timely marshalling of sufficient requisite manpower skills.
7. Government should ensure constant provision of virile and operationally-strong data in and out flow architecture for the need of the database stations as well as procure technology of the highest resolution possible to capture, distil and analyse land dataset. This effort stands to lead to speedily analysed dataset which invariably enhances real time land delivery and improves accessibility once applied.
8. It is advisable that a template should be evolved, that holistically involves all stakeholders, including the veterans, to consistently mentor upcoming land officials, so as to sustain civil service culture of objectivism and technocratic values. This no doubt will ensure continually steady legacy of forthrightness professionally, technically and managerially, which partly translates to exactitude that resources like land requires.

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